

HUMAN CAPITAL DEVELOPMENT, INSTITUTIONAL QUALITY AND GROSS DOMESTIC PRODUCT PER CAPITA: EVIDENCE FROM SELECTED SUB-SAHARAN AFRICAN COUNTRIES

SANNI, LUQMAN OLUSEGUN (Corresponding Author)

Department of Economics, Babcock University, Ilishan Remo, Ogun State, Nigeria

Sanni0468@pg.babcock.edu.ng; +234 806 285 5575

ONAKOYA, ADEGBEMI BABATUNDE

Department of Economics, Babcock University, Ilishan Remo, Ogun State, Nigeria

Gbemionakoya@gmail.com; +234 803 555 0124

TELLA, SHERRIFFDEEN ADEWALE

Department of Economics, Babcock University, Ilishan Remo, Ogun State, Nigeria

Satella@yahoo.com; +234 803 319 0791

ABSTRACT

Poverty remains a challenge in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) and the population of poor people is high and rising, compared to other regions. The region is still characterised by low levels of human capital development while conflicts, violence, corruption, and weak institutions further exacerbate the problem. This study evaluates the role of institutional quality on the relationship between human capital development and GDP per capita in SSA for the period 2004 to 2023. Data was obtained from the World Development Indicators, Worldwide Governance Indicators, the UNDP Human Development Data Centre and the Global Health Expenditure Database. The econometric techniques of ordinary least squares, fixed effect model and random effect model with Panel Corrected Standard Errors (PCSE) to correct for underperformance of other techniques. Findings reveal significant positive effect of government education expenditure on GDP per capita and significant negative influence of government health expenditure on GDP per capita. Furthermore, interaction between institutional quality and government education expenditure has negative significant impact on GDP per capita while institutional quality interaction with government health expenditure has insignificant positive effect on GDP per capita. The study recommended that the SSA governments should strengthen the institutions in SSA and then boost government human capital development spending substantially, so the expenditures can consistently and considerably improve GDPPC in SSA.

Keywords: Gross Domestic Product Per Capita, Government Education Expenditure, Government Health Expenditure, Institutional quality.

JEL Codes: E62, H51, H52, H63

1. INTRODUCTION

Poverty is endemic in Africa and parts of the developing world (World Bank 2020). Between 1990 and 2012, poverty rate had fallen from 56 percent to 43 percent in Sub Saharan Africa (SSA) but the absolute number of poor people had jumped from 280 million to 330 million people within the same period, driven by high population growth (World Bank, 2016). The World Bank Poverty and Shared Prosperity Report (2025) has shown that extreme poverty remains stubbornly high in SSA. Focus Economics (2025), in identifying the economies with the lowest GDP per capita (in U.S. dollars, current market prices) in 2025, opined that 18 of the 20 poorest are from Sub Saharan Africa (SSA). The only non-African nations in the top 20 are the conflict-riven, internationally isolated countries of Afghanistan and Yemen.

Historically nothing has worked better than economic growth in enabling societies to improve the life chances of their members, including those at the very bottom (Rodrik, 2008). The Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD, 2021) agreed with Rodrik and argued that economic growth is the most powerful instrument for reducing poverty and improving the quality of life in developing countries. Both cross-country research and country case studies provide overwhelming evidence that rapid and sustained growth is critical to faster progress in poverty reduction. Fofana et al (2023) opined that under the current situation, African countries would need to deliver higher income growth results, above 6% annual gross domestic product on average, to be able to halve poverty between 2015 and 2030. In line with the Sustainable Development Goals target of the United Nations.

The World Bank (2023) opined that economic growth offers the main path to sustained and inclusive development in Africa. Mulok et al (2012) and Amar and Pratama (2020) further argued that income growth per capita is the main source of poverty reduction in most countries while Dollar and Kraay (2016) explained, using data from over 70 countries, that high growth rates of real gross domestic product (GDP) per capita are associated with a more rapid reduction in poverty. The World Bank (2021) posits that 25 of the world's bottom 30 GDP per capita countries are in Sub-Saharan Africa. Again, the World Bank (2024) opined that per capita income in SSA, on average was projected to grow by a meagre 1.2 percent in 2024 and 1.5 percent in 2025 and that GDP per capita in about 30 percent of the region's economies, with a total human population of over 250 million, will not have fully recovered to their pre-pandemic levels. This implies that these economies will have lost several years in advancing per capita income.

Since 1990, more than 1 billion people have been lifted out of poverty globally. The decline in global extreme poverty was largely driven by robust economic growth in East Asia and Pacific and South Asia. Evidence shows that rapid economic growth between 1985 and 2001 was crucial to this enormous reduction in poverty (Lin, 2003). The World Bank (2022) updated the data by highlighting China's achievement in taking 800 million people out of extreme poverty in the 40 years between 1978 and 2018 and thereby contributing 75 percent of the entire global reduction in poverty within the same period. Mozambique illustrates the same inverse growth-poverty relationship over a shorter period. Between 1996 and 2002, the economy grew by 62 per cent and the proportion of people living in poverty declined from 69 per cent to 54 per cent (Arndt et al 2006).

Africa has vast human capital, but which would need to be harnessed and developed for sustainable growth and development. Despite some progress, Africa lags in most human capital indicators. Estimates show that the continent is operating at only 40 percent of its potential. Investments are needed in education, health, social protection and women's empowerment to enable people to become innovators, entrepreneurs and empowered citizens (World Bank, 2025). Investment in human capital through education and health is "one of the keys to poverty reduction (OECD 2002, 2022). The World Bank (2024) also opined that, across the globe, people with more education are less likely to be in poverty. 20 percent of people aged 15 or older without formal education live in extreme poverty, compared to just 3 percent of those with higher education. In Sub-Saharan Africa, the proportions are higher, but the patterns are similar. Despite this reality, the United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO) (2025) indicated that 244 million children and youth between the ages of 6 and 18 worldwide were out of school and 98 million (40 percent) of those were from Sub Saharan Africa in 2021.

Despite huge challenges with Malaria, Tuberculosis, HIV, high infant and maternal mortalities, Africa is not spending enough on the health sector while the little that is spent is not necessarily well utilised towards the intended purposes (Musah et al, 2025; Okunade et al, 2025). The World Health Organisation (WHO) estimated that in 2021, the healthcare expenditure per

capita in SSA is a meagre \$186 for each member of the population, compared to \$3,840 in the high-income countries.

Aside from other important factors, growth in Africa is also challenged by political instability, violence, terrorism and conflict which are often caused or exacerbated by growing poverty. Acemoglu et al (2008) argued that the main reason nations differ in wealth and development is institutions, not geographical factors or culture. Nations succeed when they have inclusive economic and political institutions which protect property rights and encourage widespread participation in economic and political opportunities. And nations fail when they have extractive institutions which do the opposite of the above.

Economic literature has identified institutional quality and government expenditure as factors that drive economic growth but most articles on the topic seem to ignore the relevance of institutional quality, and when they include it in their analysis, they tend to exclude the measurement of the moderating role. This study is aimed at investigating the nexus between human capital development, proxied by Government education and health expenditures, and gross domestic product per capita and the moderating effect of institutional quality in that relationship from an SSA perspective.

Arising from the above are the following questions: what is the effect of human capital development, proxied by government education and health expenditures, and institutional quality (as measured from the World Governance Indicators, WGI) on gross domestic product per capita in Sub Saharan Africa (SSA)? And what is the moderating role of institutional quality (as measured from the World Governance Indicators, WGI) in the relationship between government education and health expenditures and gross domestic product per capita in SSA? Empirical study to find credible answers to these questions would be appropriate, thereby justifying the initiative of this study. The rest of the paper is organised as follows: Section 2 reviews the relevant literature, which covers conceptual, theoretical, and empirical reviews. Section 3 details the research data and methods. Section 4 presents the research results and findings, and Section 5 discusses the findings, conclusion, and recommendation.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Conceptual Review:

2.1.1: Human Capital Development

Human capital consists of the knowledge, skills, and health that people invest in and accumulate throughout their lives, enabling them to realize their potential as productive members of society. Investing in people through nutrition, health care, quality education, jobs and skills helps develop human capital, and this is key to ending extreme poverty and creating more inclusive societies (World Bank 2019).

Shultz (1961) described human capital as the stock of skills and knowledge embodied in an individual as a result of education, training, health and other investments, which enhance the individual's productive capacity. Human capital development presupposes investments, activities, and processes that facilitate the generation of technical and expert knowledge; skills, health or values that are embodied in people. It implies maintaining an appropriate balance and key massive human resource base and providing an encouraging environment for all individuals to be fully engaged and contribute to organizational or national goals (Schultz, 1961 and Becker, 1964). Human capital can thus be divided into three key components: health, education and experience/training; and its stock could increase through better education, higher health status and new learning (Ogundari and Awokuse, 2018).

The critical elements of human capital development are built on investments in education and health. Investment in education creates new skills, knowledge and experience which stimulate

economic growth through making individuals more proficient and more productive (Bassey et al 2023; Eggoh et al, 2015).

For the purpose of this study, the reference to human capital development shall be in the context of the central government expenditures on education and health in the various countries and regions/subregions discussed in the study.

2.1.2 Government Expenditure:

Government expenditure includes all government spending or payments, usually on salaries and the acquisition or provision of goods, services and infrastructure to itself and to the society. Government spending is a major component of the national income (Dudzevičiūtė et al, 2018). The capacity of governments to improve economic and human development is a major societal concern. Miranda Lescano et al (2023) argued that public expenditure on health and education is probably one of the main instruments and basic supports of modern welfare states and certainly essential policies to improve the quality of life of their citizens. Understanding the nexus between Government expenditures on education and health and economic performance and poverty progressions is critically important to Nigeria and other African countries for their large populations and growing poverty indices.

The concept of government expenditure as used in this study is in the context of federal/central government expenditures on education and health, as a percentage of GDP, in the various countries and regions/subregions discussed in the study, and as found in the World Development Indicators (WDI) database of the World Bank and the World Health Organisation (WHO) Global Health Expenditure Database respectively.

2.1.3: Institutional Quality:

The term institutional quality is often used interchangeably with governance (Poniatowicz et al 2020). North (1990) emphasized the essential role institutions play in propelling economic growth and human development in developing, middle-income and developed countries. and defined institutions as “the rules of the game in a society or, more formally, are the humanly devised constraints that shape human interaction”. In other words, institutions help to shape social behaviour, societal norms and collective productive actions which help to achieve sustainable development in countries at whatever level of development.

Kaufmann et al (2000), Ali et al (2018), Nguyen et al (2018), World Bank (2024) further posited that good governance is strongly correlated with better development. They also found a large causal effect running from improved governance to better development outcomes. According to Nawaz et al. (2014), the theoretical model predicts that rent-seeking activities decrease with enhancement in institutional quality, which positively impacts incomes and vice versa. They argued that institutions play an important role in determining the long run economic growth in Asia. Higher levels of institutional quality have also been found to aid in attracting foreign direct investment (FDI) which, in turn, has been found to catalyse economic development (Adegboye et al 2020).

The Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI) is a World Bank project that reports aggregate and individual governance indicators for over 200 countries and territories annually from 1996. It considers six dimensions of governance: Voice and Accountability, Political Stability and Absence of Violence/Terrorism, Government Effectiveness, Regulatory Quality, Rule of Law and Control of Corruption. For the purpose of this study, institutional quality is in reference to the average of the six percentile scores of the individual countries and regions/subregions in the WGI database of the World Bank as used by Kaufmann et al (2011), Bitar et al (2021), Vu Tuan Anh and Tran Ngoc Khanh Linh (2021), Saidi et al (2024) and Ashogbon et al (2023). The averaging method is the simple average of the different indicators of institutional quality

and was chosen for its comprehensive inclusion of all the indicators as no one indicator is weighted above, or considered more important than, the others. It was also preferred due to the drawbacks of the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) such as lack of transparency and interpretability. The PCA also has high correlation requirements, shows instability across datasets and is not driven by theory.

2.2 Theoretical Review

This theoretical review aims to highlight and discuss the economic theories representing the theoretical foundation of the study.

2.2.1 Human Capital Theory

Shultz (1963) led a study to investigate why the economies of Germany and Japan recovered very quickly despite the terrible devastations of the Second World War while the United Kingdom was still rationing food long after the war. In 1960, he expounded a human capital theory with the finding that a highly educated and healthy population was behind the near miracles in Germany and Japan. A highly educated population would be highly productive while healthcare would preserve the gains of productivity made from education.

The three major findings in Shultz's theory are:

1. Countries without much human capital cannot manage physical capital effectively.
2. Economic growth can only proceed if physical capital and human capital rise together.
3. Human capital is the factor most likely to limit growth.

Shultz opined that knowledge and skills are a form of capital and an investment in human capital would enhance production and workers' earnings. Shultz then submitted that the value of labour is in its productivity. Though this was not exactly a new finding, Shultz's position was that a personal investment in one's skills and knowledge was the basis of one's productivity and indeed one's internal return. The argument was that the more cogent skills a worker possesses, the more earnings they could make. Schultz argued that education, training, healthcare and migration are forms of training and investment in people, which boost their productivity and then result in economic growth.

In summary:

Human capital results from costly investment, just like physical capital, and yields future returns in form of higher earnings or output.

Schultz provided the foundation upon which later formal growth models — like Becker's (1964) and Lucas's (1988) were built. The theory formed the theoretical underpinning for the studies by Lawanson (2017), Majumder and Biswas (2017), Ewubare and Mark (2018), Ali (2022), Sulisnaningrum (2022), Nurvita et al (2022), Nwachukwu and Oriavwote (2025)

The theory focuses heavily on the economic value of education and 'productivity' to the near complete omission of social and cultural contributions like moral, civic and religious instructions which are not necessarily evaluated and remunerated like the purely economic vocations. The theory also assumes a perfect labour market where the most 'productive' worker would be predicted to get the biggest rewards but the theory ignores the facts of market imperfections, information asymmetry, social inequalities, discriminations and other similar factors, especially in the absence of strong institutions. Lastly, the theory assumes that the ones with the most (years of) education are necessarily the most productive but that is not always the case. Despite the above possible shortcomings, the Human Capital theory has offered itself as a useful tool to evaluate the impact of human capital development on economic growth and development and is a favourite choice among researchers interested in investigating the relationships in many geographies across the globe.

2.2.2 Rostow-Musgrave theory of Government Expenditure

This model combines insights from Walt Rostow's Stages of Economic Growth (1959) and Richard Musgrave's theory of public finance (1969) which argue that the pattern and level of government expenditure of a country depend on its stage of economic development. Rostow (1960) outlined five stages of economic growth in his analysis of underdeveloped economies. The stages are listed as traditional society, preconditions to take-off, take-off, drive to maturity and age of high mass consumption. Development Economists generally agree on the centrality of government expenditure in building infrastructure and institutions to generate development. Government expenditure has been of crucial necessity to build the much-needed infrastructure to promote human welfare and economic growth, especially in the early stages of economic development. The Rostow-Musgrave theory argues that government investment in education, health, electricity, roads, water are crucial to leapfrog the economy from traditional stage to take-off stage to make for human welfare and economic development. (Edame and Fonta, 2014),

The theory argues that in early stage of economic growth, public expenditure in the economy should be encouraged. It further asserts that there is a higher tendency of market failures in the early stages of growth and the government should undertake the necessary investments to deal with these market failures. Rostow on his part claims that once the economy reaches the matured stage, the mix of public expenditure will shift from expenditure on infrastructure to increase on education, health and welfare. (Egbulonu & Ubechu, 2018).

The Musgrave theory of public expenditure (1959) postulated that at low levels of per capita income, demand for public services tends to be very low since income is devoted to satisfying primary needs (Musgrave, 1969). And when per capita income starts to rise, the demand for services supplied by the public sector such as health, education and transport begins to rise, thereby inducing the government to increase its investment in them. Consequently, as per capita income rises even further, typical of developed economies, the rate of public sector spending on utilities tends to fall as the more basic wants are being satisfied. This theory specifically related government expenditure to human capital development by using the proxies of government spending on health and education which are core to human capital development (Innocent et al, 2017). They argued that both in the short and long runs, government spending has positive but largely, insignificant impact on human capital development in Nigeria and that is why per-capita income has remained low by global standards for a long time.

There is a great measure of linearity in the assumptions of the Rostow Musgrave theory on the evolution process or developmental path for societies and without leaving room for peculiar cultural and political realities. The theory also lacks rigorous quantitative background and is mostly a product of historical observations. It does not specify the reliable or predictable timeframe within when one developmental stage ends and another begins and may therefore not be very useful at making quantitative predictions.

Be that as it may, the Rostow Musgrave theory has been quantitatively modelled by a few researchers and it has a good semblance to the historical reality of the evolution of most countries, especially, the still evolving countries of Sub Sahara Africa.

2.2.3 The Lucas model

The Lucas model, also called the Uzawa-Lucas model, learning-by-education, explains long-term economic growth as an outcome of human capital accumulation. Uzawa developed an endogenous growth model based on investment in human capital, which Lucas used. Lucas assumes that investment in education leads to human capital production, which is a crucial determinant in the growth process. He distinguishes between the internal effects of human capital where the individual worker undergoing training becomes more productive, and

external effects which spillover and increase the productivity of capital and other workers in the economy. Investing in human capital rather than physical capital has spillover effects that increase the level of technology (Jhingan, 2011).

The Uzawa-Lucas model is built on two sectors, the human capital sector (producing human capital) and the physical capital sector (producing physical capital) which are both needed for economic growth. The Uzawa-Lucas model confirms the centrality of human capital to economic growth. Lucas, along with Romer, is one of the creators of the theory of endogenous growth.

In Lucas' model, human capital is seen as a factor of production and knowledge is central to accelerating economic growth. According to Lucas' model engine of economic growth is human capital. People can use their time for work and training (i.e., research and practice). The relationship between these activities to individuals in an economy to make depends on the institutional structure and characteristics of the labour market and the economy (Tomic 2015). A unique feature of Lucas (1988) theory is that human capital is regarded as a factor of production so that increasing or constant marginal returns (non-decreasing marginal returns) to human capital accumulation can determine endogenous growth. However, growth becomes endogenous only if there are constant or increasing returns thus making Lucas-Uzawa model (Lucas 1988; Uzawa 1965) to likely be applicable to economic development (Saka and Olanipekun 2021). The Lucas model has been modified to incorporate the role of public expenditure in human capital formation. The theoretical results suggest that the growth rate will be higher if production elasticity of human capital is higher and social expenditure has significant impact on human capital formation (Sasmal & Sasmal 2023).

2.2.4 Acemoglu-Johnson-Robinson model

This model combines thoughts and insights from various studies by Daron Acemoglu, James Robinson and Simon Johnson. In their study on “The Role of Institutions in Growth and Development”, Acemoglu and Robinson (2008) posited that the causes of cross-country differences in economic development and economic growth were among the most important questions in social sciences. They wondered why some countries achieve economic growth while others stagnate. The answers to these questions will lead to the important issue of how to induce economic growth and improve living standards in society.

Output per capita, in other words, productivity, in a society, is intimately linked to the amount of human capital, physical capital and technology to which the firms and workers in that society have access. Economic growth is also related to the ability of the society to grow these factors of human capital, physical capital and technology. Technology is construed broadly to include organisational abilities, techniques and processes of production, to the extent that some countries are able to utilise their resources more efficiently than others. Connected to this subject is the phenomenon of some countries having less human capital, physical capital and technology, yet make much worse use of their factors of production and opportunities. An understanding of the answers to these questions would be needed to be able to appreciate why some countries are richer than others and why some grow faster than others. Only by understanding these issues can a reliable framework be crafted to make effective policies for growth and development.

Acemoglu and Robinson argued that institutions (very broadly construed) are the fundamental causes of economic growth and development divergence among countries and it is possible to develop a coherent framework to understand why and how institutions differ, as well as how they change, across countries. Acemoglu, Johnson, and Robinson (AJR) argue that institutions, not geography, culture, or policy alone, are the fundamental cause of long-run economic growth and prosperity.

Abdulrahman (2022) employed the Lucas theory while Sasmal and Sasmal (2023) deployed the Modified Lucas model as the theoretical backgrounds to their studies. In order to investigate the relative contribution of human capital development and institutional quality to GDP per capita growth and, ultimately, poverty reduction, this study considered the Acemoglu et al (2014) theory and adapted it into the Lucas (1988) theory as done by Bastos, Gama and Assis (2020). In other words, this study proposes a modified version of Lucas 1988 theory through inclusion of institutional quality as accelerator for human capital and a vital determinant of economic growth.

2.3 Empirical Review

There is considerable literature on the relationship and causality between human capital development and poverty reduction as represented by economic growth/GDP Per Capita. The findings from the various studies have shown divergent results on the effect of human capital investment on economic growth and potential reduction in poverty.

Akombor et al (2025) investigated the public expenditure-poverty nexus in Nigeria (1999-2024) using the cointegration and ARDL methodologies. The study found health expenditure proving most effective for both short and long-run poverty reduction while education spending shows counterproductive short-run effects but positive long-run impacts, indicating implementation inefficiencies. Dankumo et al (2024) looked at the effect of health and education spending by government in reducing poverty in Nigeria from 1996-2021 employing the ARDL bounds test methodology. Results of the analysis showed that spending on education and health expenditures are all significant at a 5 percent level of significance and are positively related to the dependent variable implying that on average, the higher the education and health expenditure, the higher the poverty reduction, *ceteris paribus*

Salami et al (2025) utilized panel data from five Anglophone West African countries from 1990 to 2023. The Feasible Generalized Least Squares (FGLS) estimation confirmed that government expenditure on education has a positive and significant effect on economic growth.

The study by Amirov et al (2026), investigated the relationship between human capital, represented by government education and health expenditures, and economic growth in five Central Asian countries: Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan. It found strong positive long run relationship between human capital and growth. Natarajan (2026) study examined the role of human capital in shaping growth in Bahrain, Oman, and

Saudi Arabia from 2004 to 2022, highlighting its asymmetric and shock-sensitive nature

in resource-dependent economies. The study used panel fixed effects with Driscoll–Kraay corrections, Fisher-type cointegration, nonlinear ARDL (NARDL) models, Toda–Yamamoto causality, and Bai–Perron structural break tests. Results reveal that fiscal expansions in health are strongly growth-enhancing, while contractions impose disproportionately larger costs, underscoring the opportunity cost of austerity.

Keji (2021) examined the relationship between human capital and economic growth in Nigeria between 1981 and 2017 and discovered a significant positive long-run relationship between human capital and economic growth. Though Keji aimed to examine the education and health human capital variables, the variables used had no health component in the analysis. The education variable was also just Student Enrolment with no demarcation among the primary, secondary and tertiary segments. Moreover, the study did not consider the element of institutional quality, which would appear to have an a-priori relevance to a study of this nature in the Nigerian environment

The findings in the foregoing studies aligned with Appiah (2017) in the investigation of the impact of government education spending on selected developing countries, including Sub Saharan Africa. The study used the 'system' Generalised Method of Moments estimator and found that expansion in education expenditure in developing countries affects per capita GDP positively. Ojo and Ojo (2022), using the Error Correction Model, also found that government expenditure on education and health produced positive and significant impact on economic growth and interaction. They therefore concluded that education and health expenditure have an impact on economic development. The foregoing studies agree with Sasmal and Sasmal (2023) who investigated the impact of government social spending on education on economic growth in the Indian context. Using panel regressions, the study found that higher social expenditure results in higher literacy rate which then has significant positive effect on per capita income.

Andabai and Eze (2018) could however, only find a positive and significant relationship between education expenditure and economic growth but not health expenditure and economic growth in Nigeria while Adekoya (2018), using the Vector Error Correction Error Model (VECM), could only establish a positive long run relationship between government expenditure on health and GDP per capita but a negative long run relationship between government expenditure on education and GDP per capita in Nigeria in the years 1995 to 2017. Nwachukwu and Oriavwute (2025), utilising the ARDL (Autoregressive Distributed Lag) model also discovered that Government Recurrent and Capital Health Expenditures and Human Capital Formation were all positive, but only the recurrent expenditure was a significant determinant of the GDP per capita in Nigeria in 1981 to 2024.

Eggoh et al (2015) concluded that the relationship between human capital (measured by education and health related variables) and economic growth was negative for a large sample of 49 African countries over the period from 1996 to 2010. Using traditional cross-section and dynamic panel techniques, the finding was that public expenditures on education and health have a negative impact on economic growth. Similar to the foregoing was the finding by Suwandaru et al. (2021) on the Indonesia dataset covering the years 1988 to 2018. The study, using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) bound test method, found that public expenditure on education has an insignificant relationship with economic growth in the short and long runs. Following the same trend, Wang et al. (2021) analysed the impact of health human capital on poverty in Sub-Saharan Africa but found no evidence of significant association between health human capital and poverty in Sub Sahara Africa in the long run while health human capital has a significant effect on poverty reduction only in the short term. Similarly, Lawanson (2017) could not establish a positive contribution of government expenditures on education and health to economic growth except in their recurrent components. By the findings of the Lawanson study, the capital votes on government expenditures on education and health have no link to economic growth. Similarly, Adelowokan et al (2020), using the Pooled Mean Group (PMG) estimation model on a Sub-Saharan African (SSA) countries dataset from 1999 to 2016, found that fiscal policy does not have poverty reduction impact in the region. Emeghara et al (2021) also opined that Government Expenditures on Education and on Health did not have any positive or significant influence on economic growth in Nigeria except for Government Expenditure on Education which only impacted positively and significantly in the short run. These negative findings seem to agree with a good number of other studies, especially on the SSA and developing countries, apparently due to serious institutional quality weaknesses and attendant leakages.

Nguyen et al. (2018) focused on the roles of institutional quality on economic growth which they perceived were still heavily debated in the literature. Their study investigated the impacts of institutional quality on economic growth for 29 emerging economies over the 2002-2015 period by employing System Generalized Method of Moments (SGMM) estimators. They

found the significant positive impacts of institutional quality on economic growth. The institutional quality impedes the positive effects of foreign direct investments (FDIs) and trade openness on economic growth. However, institutional quality improvement can mitigate the competition brought by trade openness in the areas FDIs operate to optimize their spill-over effect.

Dankumo et al (2023) also investigated the role of governance in the impacts of government expenditure on poverty. The study deployed a System Generalised Methods of Moments (SGMM) econometric technique with unbalanced panel data of 46 countries in the Sub-Saharan African region covering the period 1996 to 2019 and confirmed that the problems of governance (corruption and political instability) and public expenditure aggravate poverty. The marginal effect also showed that low governance, at both medium and minimum levels, aggravates poverty. However, governance is insignificant at the maximum levels, suggesting that corruption and political instability have an important role in mediating the consequences of government expenditure on poverty in the sample countries.

Ali et al. (2018) equally introduced other conditions or variables which they believe strengthen human capital to positively impact on economic growth. Using data for 132 countries over 15 years, the empirical results reveal that human capital plays a positive role in per capita GDP growth only in the presence of better economic opportunities and high-quality legal institutions. In the study by Sanni and Onakoya (2025), they examined the impact of human capital development, proxied by government expenditures on education and health, and institutional quality on GDP per capita, a common proxy for poverty, in Nigeria for the period, 1989 to 2022. The Autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) was employed with result showing a positive significant effect of Government Expenditure on Education on GDP per capita whereas Government Expenditure on Health brought about a significant negative effect during the years of the study. Further findings showed institutional quality demonstrating a negative and significant effect on GDP per capita. This was corroborated by Ashogbon et al (2023) in a study which established that institutional quality had significant negative effect on economic growth in the long run with no such evidence shown in the short run.

The empirical literature reveals complex and often conflicting relationships among the variables in a manner that challenges simple input-output models of the impact of government expenditure. Regardless of divergence in sample periods or variables or methodologies or theories used, much of the literature found weak effects of government spending on economic growth in SSA and in developing countries. „As postulated by theory and supported by literature, institutional quality would be an important element in the effectiveness of government human capital expenditures and GDP per capita but institutional quality is absent in most of the available studies. Among the relatively few studies which investigated institutional quality, the important question of its moderating effect in the relationship between human capital development and GDP per capita has not been well investigated. This study aims to fill that gap by investigating, not only the effect of institutional quality and human capital development on GDP per capita but also the moderating effect of institutional quality in the relationship between the latter two.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework of this study is built on the Lucas (1988) endogenous growth model and augmented by Acemoglu and Robinson (2010) roles of institutions in growth process. The central proposition of Lucas (1988) theory that took root from Uzawa (1965) is that investment in human capital (education, health, public goods etc.) is a crucial determining factor in economic growth. Given a Cobb-Douglas production function, Lucas (1988) postulates that the

level of economic activity is dependent on the quantum of physical capital, human capital, and a set of factors that are constant over time. Thus, the model is specified as:

$$Y_t = Ak_t^\beta (u_t h_t)^{1-\beta} \quad (3.1)$$

where, Y denotes the level of economic activity of a particular country at time t . A is a constant while k and h are respectively physical capital and human capital accumulation over a given period, and u denotes the fraction of human capital devoted to production. According to Bastos, Gama and Assis (2020), Lucas (1988) failed to explicitly identify with the role of institutions in economic growth process. Thus, institutional differences in economic growth process will be captured within the constant parameter of Lucas (1988) model. Hence, institutions' effect on the economic growth would not be modelled.

Following Acemoglu et al. (2014) and adapting Bastos, Gama and Assis (2020), this study proposes a modified version of Lucas 1988 theory through inclusion of institutional quality as accelerator for human capital and a vital determinant of economic growth. This suggests that differences in economic growth across countries is attributable to institutional quality. Therefore, a re-specification of equation (3.1) yields the following:

$$Y_t = Ak_t^\beta (u_t h_t I_t)^{1-\beta} \quad 0 < \beta < 1; 0 < u_t < 1 \quad (3.2)$$

3.2 Model Specification

Adapting and modifying Bastos, Gama and Assis (2020), through decomposition of institutions, the model for the study is specified as:

$$\begin{aligned} GDPPC_{it} = & \varphi_0 + \varphi_1 GCF_{it} + \varphi_2 LBFP_{it} + \varphi_3 GED_{it} + \varphi_4 GEH_{it} + \varphi_5 ISQ_{it} \\ & + \varphi_6 (GED * ISQ)_{it} + \varphi_7 (GEH * ISQ)_{it} \\ & + u_{it} \end{aligned} \quad (3.3)$$

where, $GDPPC$ is gross domestic product per capita, GCF denotes gross capital formation, $LBFP$ depicts labour force participation rate, GED represents government education expenditure (investment in human capital), GEH depicts government health expenditure (also, investment in human capital) and ISQ denotes institutional quality. $(GED * ISQ)$ and $(GEH * ISQ)$ denote the interactions of institutional quality with government education expenditure and government health expenditure respectively. Country specific identity is represented as i , while t denotes period and $\varphi_1, \varphi_2, \varphi_3, \varphi_4, \varphi_5, \varphi_6$ and φ_7 as the respective elasticities of $GCF, LBFP, GED, GEH, ISQ, (GED * ISQ)$ and $(GEH * ISQ)$ with φ_0 as the intercept.

3.3 Data Sources:

Secondary data for 25 selected countries in Sub Saharan Africa covering 2004 to 2023 sourced from the World Development Indicators (WDI), Global Health Expenditure Database (GHED) and Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI) were used in this study. The countries are Angola, Benin Republic, Botswana, Burundi, Cameroon, Central African Republic, Chad, Djibouti, Ethiopia, Gabon, Gambia, Ghana, Guinea, Kenya, Malawi, Mali, Mozambique, Namibia, Niger, Nigeria, Rwanda, South Africa, Tanzania, Uganda and Zambia.

3.4: Estimation Method:

Model Selection/Diagnostic Test

The outcome of the diagnostic tests was used to determine the appropriate model for result interpretation and hypothesis testing. There is evidence of non-essential multicollinearity due to interaction of variables, hence the VIF mean is 19.22. The F-testparm was used to choose between OLS and FEM, and with F-statistics = 12.35 and prob = 0.00 < 0.05, suggesting that FEM is preferred to OLS. The Breusch-Pagan LM test for decision between OLS and REM

with chi-square of 0.00 and prob = 1.00 > 0.05 signifies preference for OLS. However, the Hausman test result employed to choose between FEM and REM returned chi-square = -7.12 indicating inconclusive outcome. Notwithstanding, the Modified Wald test for heteroskedasticity with chi-square = 2561.25 and prob = 0.00 < 0.05 connotes that variances of the error terms are not constant over time, suggesting presence of heteroskedasticity. Furthermore, the Woodridge test for serial or autocorrelation returned F-statistics = 46.1398 and prob = 0.00 < 0.05 indicating evidence of serial correlation. Thus, panel-corrected standard error (PCSE) is considered suitable for interpretation and hypothesis testing because it can resolve the cross-sectional dependence and serial correlation issues present in the model (Reed & Yu, 2011).

PCSE is a sophisticated technique which accounts for cross-sectional dependence, heteroscedasticity, and autocorrelation. The PCSE estimator yields robust estimates when the number of cross-sections (N) is greater than the time dimension (T). Given that the cross-sectional units exceed the time dimension, the PCSE model is therefore appropriate for our situation (Bailey & Katz, 2011).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.1 Descriptive Statistics:

The characteristics of the data series as revealed through descriptive statistics that include measures of central tendency, variability, and probability distribution are presented in Table 4.1,1

Table 4.1.1: Descriptive Statistics

F. SAMPLE	GDPPC	GCF	LBFP	GEE	GEH	ISQ
<i>OBS</i>	499	455	496	419	456	500
<i>MEAN</i>	1920.921	6.74e+11	68.394	3.893	5.015	31.229
<i>MAX</i>	10219.11	5.83e+13	89.428	10.826	11.000	74.103
<i>MIN</i>	125.195	-5.32e+08	32.476	0.319	2.000	5.003
<i>STD. DEV</i>	2171.683	4.30e+12	12.206	2.050	2.014	16.740
<i>SKEWNESS</i>	1.794	9.194	-0.847	1.037	0.930	0.652
<i>KURTOSIS</i>	5.165	101.754	3.517	4.114	3.070	2.791
<i>J. BERA</i>	365.295	191297	64.809	96.843	65.786	36.35
<i>PROB.</i>	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000

GEE and GEH have the least standard deviations with values lower than their mean. LBFP and ISQ also have standard deviations lower than their mean values. This implies that the data series clusters around the mean for the four variables. With their high Jarque-Bera statistics and the associated low probabilities of under 0.05, indicating statistical significance, it is evident that the data series do not exhibit normal distribution for all the variables.

4.2: Cross-Sectional Dependence

This is a common feature of panel data study that arises due to combination of factors such as presence of common shocks and unobserved components that becomes part of the error structure. The increased integration of economic and financial events across the globe that connotes strong interdependencies among the cross-sectional units and remains a major challenge in econometric analysis.

Table 4.2.1: Cross-Sectional Dependence Test

Test	Statistic	Prob.
Breusch-Pagan LM	122.6087	0.00***
Pesaran scaled LM	15.67856	0.00***
Pesaran CD	2.571114	0.01**

Author’s compilation, 2026 with EViews 12

Note: Standard errors in parentheses; ***, **, * denote 1%; 5% and 10% significant levels respectively

The results of cross-sectional dependence test presented in Table 4.2.1 revealed evidence of cross-sectional dependence among the variables.

4.3: Panel Unit Root Test

The results of the panel unit root test are presented in Table 4.3.1 below. Three different unit root test tools were used in this study. Two test tools each for first-and-second generations with Levin, Lin and Chu (LLC) and Im, Pesaran and Shin (IPS) representing the first-generation test tools. The first-generation panel unit root test tools are flawed on the ground of the assumption of homogeneity of independent variables because cross-sectional dependency is not considered. In response to the shortcomings associated with the first-generation unit root tests, the second-generation unit root test tool of Corrected Im, Pesaran and Shin (CIPS) deployed in this study with the result reported in Table 4.3.1.

Table 4.3.1: Unit Root Test

Variables	Level			First Difference			Remarks
	LLC	IPS	CIPS	LLC	IPS	CIPS	
LNGDPPC	-5.741**	-2.389***	-2.037*	N/A	N/A	-5.544***	I(0), I(1)
LNGCF	-0.546	-	-1.337	-7.754***	-	-3.758***	I(1)
LNLBFP	-2.934***	-1.489	-1.493	N/A	-3.365***	-3.084***	I(0), I(1)
GEE	-4.462***	-2.587***	-2.484***	N/A	N/A	N/A	I(0)
GEH	1.020	-	-1.606	1.554	-	-3.661***	I(1)
ISQ	-4.258***	-1.693	-2.267***	N/A	-4.449***	N/A	I(0), I(1)

Author’s compilation, 2026 with Stata 18

Note: Standard errors in parentheses; ***, **, * denote 1%; 5% and 10% significant levels respectively

Note: Gross Domestic Product Per Capita (GDPPC), Gross Capital Formation (GCF), Labour Force Participation (LBFP), Government Expenditure on Education to Gross Domestic Product (GEE), Government Expenditure on Health to GDP (GEH) and Institutional Quality (ISQ).

The results of unit root test reported in Table 4.3.1 reveal that the variables used in the study exhibit different orders of integration. Whereas LNGDPPC, LNLBFP and ISQ are stationary at levels and first difference, GEE is levels stationary while LNGCF and GEH are stationary at first difference.

Table 4.4: Effect of interaction between institutional quality and government education and health expenditures on GDP per capita in Sub Saharan Africa: DV - LNGDPPC

VARIABLES	OLS	FEM	REM	PCSE
LNGCF	0.1880*** (0.0161)	0.3140*** (0.0376)	0.1880*** (0.0161)	0.1880*** (0.0118)

LNLBFP	-1.2837*** (0.2224)	-1.0130*** (0.3042)	-1.2837*** (0.2224)	-1.2837*** (0.1415)
GEE	0.1066* (0.0596)	-0.0462 (0.0877)	0.1066* (0.0596)	0.1066*** (0.0374)
GEH	-0.1319* (0.0780)	-0.1040 (0.0676)	-0.1319* (0.0780)	-0.1319** (0.0780)
ISQ	0.0247** (0.0097)	-0.0006 (0.0101)	0.0247** (0.0097)	0.0247*** (0.0090)
GEE*ISQ	-0.0028** (0.0013)	-0.0004 (0.0019)	-0.0028** (0.0013)	-0.0028** (0.0011)
GEH*ISQ	0.0001 (0.0023)	0.0023 (0.0020)	0.0001 (0.0023)	0.0001 (0.0021)
Constant	7.7522*** (0.6771)	4.4004*** (1.4582)	7.7522*** (0.6771)	7.7522*** (0.4982)
Observations	116	116	116	116
Number of c_id	7	7	7	7
R-squared	0.7884	0.7580	0.9414	0.7884
Adj. R-squared	0.7747	0.5	0.7884	0.7747
F-Statistics	F(7, 108) = 57.49 Prob > F = 0.00	F(7, 102) = 15.82 Prob > F = 0.00	Wald chi ² (7) = 191.42 Prob > chi2 = 0.00	Wald chi ² (7) = 477.33 Prob > chi2 = 0.00
Multicollinearity Test VIF Mean	19.22	-	-	-
F-Testparm	-	F(6, 102) = 12.35 Prob > F = 0.00	-	-
Breusch-Pagan LM Test	-		Chibar ² (01) = 0.00 Prob>Chibar ² = 1.00	
Hausman Test	-	-	Chi ² = -7.12 Inconclusive	
Modified Wald Test for Heteroskedasticity	-	Chi ² (7) = 2561.25 Prob > chi ² = 0.00	-	-
Woodridge Test for Autocorrelation	-	F(1, 6) = 46.139 Prob > F = 0.00	-	-

Note: Standard errors in parentheses; *, **, * denote 1%; 5% and 10% significant levels respectively**

Note: Gross Domestic Product Per Capita (GDPPC), Gross Capital Formation (GCF), Labour Force Participation (LBFP), Government Expenditure on Education to Gross Domestic Product (GEE), Government Expenditure on Health to GDP (GEH) and Institutional Quality (ISQ), interaction between government expenditure on education and institutional quality as well interaction between government expenditure on health and institutional quality.

The parameter estimates for interpretation and hypothesis testing reported in column five of Table 4.2.3 is reproduced in equations (4.1) and (4.2)

$$LNGDPPC_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1LNGCF_{it} + \beta_2LNLBFP_{it} + \beta_3GEE_{it} + \beta_4GEH_{it} + \beta_5ISQ_{it} + \beta_6(GEE * ISQ)_{it} + \beta_7(GEH * ISQ)_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (4.1)$$

$$LNGDPPC_{it} = 7.7522 + 0.1880LNGCF_{it} - 1.2837LNLBFP_{it} + 0.1066GEE_{it} - 0.1319GEH_{it} + 0.0247ISQ_{it} - 0.0028(GEE * ISQ)_{it} + 0.0001(GEH * ISQ)_{it} \quad (4.2)$$

From equation (4.2), there is evidence that labour force participation, government expenditure on health and the interaction between government expenditure on education and institutional quality have negative relationship with gross domestic product per capita. This suggests that increase in labour force participation, government expenditure on health and the interaction between government expenditure on education and institutional quality would lead to decrease in gross domestic product per capita. Thus, a 1 percent increase in labour force participation, government expenditure on health and the interaction between government expenditure on education, and institutional quality would respectively cause 1.2837, 0.1319 and 0.0028 percent decrease in gross domestic product, *ceteris paribus*. Labour force participation, government expenditure on health and the interaction between government expenditure on education and institutional quality are statistically significant at 1%, 5% and 5% respectively, signifying that they are important variables that influence changes in gross domestic product per capita in the selected sub-Saharan African during the period of the study.

Conversely, there is evidence that gross capital formation, government expenditure on education, institutional quality and interaction of government expenditure on health with institutional quality have positive relationship with gross domestic product per capita. This connotes that gross domestic product per capita would increase because of increase in gross capital formation, government expenditure on education, institutional quality and interaction of government expenditure on health with institutional quality. Thus, a 1 percent increase in gross capital formation, government expenditure on education, institutional quality, and interaction of government expenditure on health with institutional quality would lead to increase in gross domestic product per capita by 0.1880, 0.1066, 0.0247 and 0.0001 respectively, *other things being equal*. Gross capital formation, government expenditure on education and institutional quality are statistically significant at 1% apiece and are important factors that affect gross domestic product per capita in the selected sub-Saharan Africa. Interaction of institutional quality with government education expenditure is significant (prob = 0.02 < 0.05), its interaction with government health expenditure is insignificant (prob = 0.97 > 0.05).

In summary, government education expenditure was positive and significant but the magnitude was very low at 0.1066 while government health expenditure was negative and significant. The interaction of institutional quality with government education expenditure was negative and significant while the interaction of institutional quality with government health expenditure was positive with a very low magnitude of 0.0001 and was insignificant.

The overall goodness fit as indicated by the Wald chi-squares that test the null hypothesis that all coefficients in the model are zero has chi-squares statistics is 477.33 with probability of 0.00 < 0.01 and significant at the 1% level, implying that the model is a good fit for the data. This demonstrates that the variables are jointly significant factors affecting changes in gross domestic product per capita in the selected sub-Saharan Africa during the period of the study.

4.3 Discussion of Findings

The empirical findings of Appiah (2017), Andabai and Eze (2018), Keji (2021), Ojo and Ojo (2022), Sasmal and Sasmal (2023), Akombor et al (2024), Dankumo et al (2024), Salami et al (2025), Sanni and Onakoya (2025) and Amirov et al (2026) provided evidence of positive relationships between government education expenditure and economic growth, thereby aligning with the finding of this study. On the other hand, Adekoya (2018), Ojo and Ojo (2022) and Amirov et al (2026) found a similar positive and significant long run relationship between Government Expenditure on Health and economic growth, contradicting the finding of this study in the process. The findings in the foregoing studies align with economic theory on, at

least, one of the two expenditure variables and encourage additional government spending on the affected expenditure variable.

A conspicuous observation from the above is that, in most of the studies, even where a particular expenditure head shows a positive and significant relationship, the magnitude is usually very low, meaning that so much more scarce resources would need to be deployed to effect the desired positive results.

In contrast to those findings were the research conclusions of Emeghara et al (2021) that government expenditures on education and on health did not have any positive or significant influence on economic growth in Nigeria except for government expenditure on education which only impacted positively and significantly on economic growth in the short run. Aside this short run impact, the study found that government expenditures on education and health did not stimulate growth in Nigeria, contrary to economic theory. Almost in sync with the foregoing, Lawanson (2017) could not establish a positive contribution of government expenditures on education and health to economic growth except in their recurrent components. By the findings of the Lawanson study, the capital votes on government expenditures on education and health have no link to economic growth. Eggoh et al (2015) also concluded that the relationship between human capital (measured by education and health related variables) and economic growth was negative for a large sample of 49 African countries while Adelowokan et al (2020) found that fiscal policy does not have poverty reduction impact in the region. Most of the studies revealed that, relative to the rest of the world, the effects of government expenditures on education and health are extremely low and are not major contributors to economic growth in Sub-Saharan Africa. These findings contrast partially with this study which found a long run positive relationship between government education expenditure and GDP per capita though the magnitude is very low indeed. Government health expenditure was negative and significant and corroborated the findings in the aforementioned studies. The low impact of the government education and health expenditures on growth may not necessarily emanate only from the quantity or level of the expenditures but also from the allocation and deployment of the funds, given the low institutional quality scores associated with the SSA countries. This is likely to suggest that public spending, within the study context, may not be efficiently allocated toward growth-enhancing projects in SSA.

On institutional quality, Nguyen et al (2018) found significant positive impacts of institutional quality on economic growth but the interaction of institutional quality impedes the positive effects of foreign direct investments (FDIs) and trade openness on economic growth, which corroborates the findings of this study in the weakening interactive effect of institutional quality on the relationships between the government expenditure types and GDP per capita. On the other hand, Ali et al. (2018) confirmed that human capital plays a positive role in per capita GDP growth only in the presence of better economic opportunities and high-quality legal institutions. This is a corroboration of the positive interactive effect of institutional quality on growth as opined by theory but is in contrast with the finding of this study.

In line with the finding of this study is the finding by Dankumo et al (2023) that institutional quality at low or medium levels, may be injurious to growth and poverty reduction. This was corroborated by Ashogbon et al (2023) in a study which established that institutional quality had significant negative effect on economic growth in the long run with no such evidence shown in the short run.

Theoretically, the conclusions of this study find corroboration in the Uzawa-Lucas model, Learning-by-education, which explains long term economic growth as an outcome of human capital accumulation, namely the investment in education. Also related to the above is the Shultz (1963) Human Capital Theory that a highly educated population would be highly productive while healthcare would preserve the gains of productivity made from education.

SSA has not been investing appreciably in developing its huge human capital stock, thereby causing the potential for its population boom to become a burden. The foregoing is also in tandem with the Acemoglu, Johnson and Robinson (2001) principle which argued that the main reason nations differ in wealth and development is institutions, not geographical factors or culture.

5: Conclusions and recommendations:

The study concludes that government expenditures on education and health are not producing appreciable effects on poverty, represented by GDP per capita, while the interaction of institutional quality is also not yielding the salutary developmental outcomes expected by theory. This suggests that the governments' fiscal spendings play a very limited role in influencing growth outcomes and institutional quality also impedes economic growth in the sample countries. The combined effect of the foregoing may be the causative factor behind SSA's stagnated GDP per capita records over the past several years.

Rather than indicating that government expenditure or institutional quality is inherently detrimental to growth, the result points to structural inefficiencies, weak institutional quality, and possible misallocation of resources. Furthermore, the results imply that increases in expenditure without corresponding improvements in efficiency may not yield meaningful growth outcomes.

The relevance of the appropriate levels and judiciousness of government human development expenditures and strong institutional quality cannot be overemphasised within the policy framework to grow, appreciably, the GDP per capita base and reduce poverty in SSA.

In light of these findings, policy efforts should prioritize improving the quality, composition and utilisation of public expenditure even while paying attention to volume. In this regard, greater emphasis should be placed on project selection to prioritise growth-enhancing and poverty-reducing expenditure in infrastructure, education, and health, while reducing wastages and non-productive recurrent spending that have been long associated with government spending in SSA. Additionally, anti-corruption enforcement and general strengthening of the institutional framework should be pursued to enhance transparency and accountability in public financial management. Specifically, fiscal accountability reforms are needed to ensure performance-based budgeting and transparent procurement that are critical to ensuring that government spending translates into tangible economic growth. Efficient and digitized budget tracking and auditing systems need to be put in place by the SSA governments while judicial reforms must be implemented to facilitate quick dispensation of justice as a consequence management and deterrent solution to corruption. Future research should also consider disaggregating expenditure components and exploring nonlinear relationships to better capture the dynamics between public spending and growth.

REFERENCES

- Acemoglu, D., Johnson, S., & Robinson, J. A. (2001). The colonial origins of comparative development: An empirical investigation. *American economic review*, 91(5), 1369-1401.
- Adegboye, F. B., Osabohien, R., Olokoyo, F. O., Matthew, O., & Adediran, O. (2020). Institutional quality, foreign direct investment, and economic development in sub-Saharan Africa. *Humanities and social sciences communications*, 7(1), 1-9.
- Adekoya, O. D. (2018). Impact of human capital development on poverty alleviation in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics & Management Sciences*, 7(4).

<https://doi.org/10.4172/2162-6359.1000544>

- Adelowokan, O. A., Mosunmola Osoba, O., & Ajibowo, S. A. (2020). Fiscal Policy and Poverty Reduction in Some Selected Sub-Saharan Africa Countries. *International Journal of Social Sciences (IJSS)*, 10(1), 1-10.
- Akombor, T., Ilemona, A., & Gimba, O. J. (2025). Public Expenditure And Poverty Reduction In Nigeria: A Sectoral Analysis. *Journal of Economics and Allied Research* 10 (4) 1-14
- Amar, S., & Pratama, I. (2020). Exploring the link between income inequality, poverty reduction and economic growth: An ASEAN perspective. *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change*, 11(2), 24-41.
- Amirov, A., Nurimbetov, R., Arabov, N., Boltaev, B., Hasanov, H., & Nasimov, I. (2026). Exploring the Dynamics of Human Capital and Economic Growth in Central Asian Countries: An Empirical Analysis Using Panel Data. *Global Business Review. Advance online publication*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09721509251415274>
- Andabai, P. W., & Eze, G. P. (2017). Empirical investigation of human capital investment and its effects on economic growth in Nigeria. *European Journal of Business and Innovation Research*, 6 (6), 73-80. <https://www.eajournals.org>
- Appiah, E. N. (2017). The effect of education expenditure on per capita GDP in developing countries. *International Journal of Economics and Finance*, 9(10), 136-144.
- Arndt, C., James, R. C., & Simler, K. R. (2006). Has economic growth in Mozambique been pro-poor?. *Journal of African Economies*, 15(4), 571-602.
- Ashogbon, F. O., Onakoya, A. B., Obiakor, R. T., & Lawal, E (2023). Public debt, institutional quality and economic growth: evidence from Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Allied Research*, 8(1), 93-107.
- Bassey, G. E., Ekong, U. M., & Ekpenyong, B. E. (2023). Government expenditure and human capital development in Nigeria. *Advances in Social Sciences and Management*, 1(1), 1-21.
- Bastos, S. Q. D. A., Gama, F., & Assis, T. D. P (2020). Acemoglu meets Lucas: Institutions, human capital and economic growth. *International Journal of Business Administration*. 11(4), 98-114
- <https://doi.org/10.5430/ijba.v11n4p98>
- Becker, G.S (1964): Human Capital: A theoretical and empirical analysis, with special reference to education: New York: National Bureau of Economic research, distributed by Columbia University Press
- <https://www.nber.org/books-and-chapters/human-capital-theoretical-and-empirical-analysis-special-reference-education-first-edition>
- Bitar, M., Naceur, S. B., Ayadi, R., & Walker, T. (2021). Basel compliance and financial stability: Evidence from Islamic banks. *Journal of Financial Services Research*, 60(1), 81-134.
- Dankumo, A. M., Ishak, S., Auta, Y., & Denthe, A. (2023). Impact of public expenditure on poverty: role of governance. *Jurnal Ekonomi Malaysia*, 57(1), 113-126.

- Dankumo, A. M., Shido-Ikwu, S. B., Ibrahim, J. I. M. O. H., & Auta, Y. U. S. U. F. (2024). Impact of health and education expenditures on poverty reduction in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Allied Research*, 9(2), 45-55.
- Dollar, D., Kleineberg, T., & Kraay, A. (2016). Growth still is good for the poor. *European Economic Review*, 81, 68-85.
- Dudzevičiūtė, G., Šimelytė, A., & Liučvaitienė, A. (2018). Government expenditure and economic growth in the European Union countries. *International Journal of Social Economics*, 45(2), 372-386.
- Edame, G. E., & Fonta, W. M. (2014). The impact of government expenditure on infrastructure in Nigeria: A co-integration & error correction specification. *International Journal of African and Asian Studies*, 3(2), 40-56.
- Egbulonu, K. G., & Ubechu, T. N. (2018). Public expenditure and Nigeria's economic growth (1970–2015). *International Journal of Innovative Finance and Economics Research*, 6(3), 74-89.
- Egogh, J., Houeninvo, H., & Sossou, G. A. (2015). Education, health and economic growth in African countries. *Journal of Economic Development, Chung-Ang University, Department of Economics* 40 (1), 93-111
- Focus Economics (2025): Top 20 Poorest Countries in the World in 2026
<https://www.focus-economics.com/blog/the-poorest-countries-in-the-world/>
- Fofana, I., Chitiga-Mabugu, M., & Mabugu, R. E. (2023). Is Africa on track to ending poverty by 2030? *Journal of African Economies*, 32(Supplement_2), ii87-ii98.
- Innocent, M. N. J., Job, M. N., Okeke, A., & Aondo, D. C. (2017). Government expenditure and human capital development in Nigeria: an auto-regressive distributed lagged model approach (ARDL). *International Journal of Advanced Studies in Economics and Public Sector Management* 5 (1), 143-158
- Jhingam, M. L. (2011). *The economics of development and planning*. Delhi: Vrinda Publications.
- Kaufmann, Daniel; Kraay, Aart; Zoido-Lobaton, Pablo (2000): Governance Matters: From Measurement To Action. *IMF: Finance and Development: June 2000*
<https://www.imf.org/external/pubs/ft/fandd/2000/06/pdf/kauf.pdf>
- Kaufmann, D., Kraay, A., & Mastruzzi, M. (2011). The worldwide governance indicators: Methodology and analytical issues1. *Hague journal on the rule of law*, 3(2), 220-246.
- Keji, S. A. (2021). Human capital and economic growth in Nigeria. *Future Business Journal*, 7(1):49, 1-8
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s43093-021-00095-4>
- Lawanson, O. I. (2017). Human capital investment and economic development in Nigeria: A focus on education and health. *Journal of Economics and Policy Analysis*, 2(1), 95-112.
- Lucas Jr, R. E. (1988). On the mechanics of economic development. *Journal of monetary economics*, 22(1), 3-42.

- Majumder, S., & Biswas, S. C. (2017). The role of education in poverty alleviation: Evidence from Bangladesh. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 8(20), 151-160.
- Miranda-Lescano, R., Muinelo-Gallo, L., & Roca-Sagalés, O. (2023). Human development and decentralization: The importance of public health expenditure. *Annals of Public and Cooperative Economics*, 94(1), 191-219.
- Mulok, D., Kogid, M., Asid, R., & Lily, J. (2012). Is economic growth sufficient for poverty alleviation? Empirical evidence from Malaysia. *Cuadernos de economía*, 35(97), 26-32.
- Musah, A., Aawaar, G., Musah, G., & Abdul-Mumuni, A. (2025). Financial development, public health financing, and health outcomes in Sub-Saharan Africa. *BMC Public Health*, 25(1), 29-43.
- Musgrave, R. A. (1969). Cost-benefit analysis and the theory of public finance. *Journal of Economic Literature*, 7(3), 797-806.
- Natarajan, V. K. (2026). Human capital and growth in the Gulf: Evidence from panel econometrics, asymmetric dynamics, and structural breaks. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 14(1), 2624873.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/23322039.2026.2624873>
- Nguyen, C. P., Su, T. D., & Nguyen, T. V. H. (2018). Institutional quality and economic growth: The case of emerging economies. *Theoretical Economics Letters*, 8(11), 1943-1956.
- Nketiah-Amponsah, E. (2019). The impact of health expenditures on health outcomes in sub-Saharan Africa. *Journal of Developing Societies*, 35(1), 134-152
- North, D. C. (1990). *Institutions, institutional change and economic performance*. Cambridge university press.
- Nurvita, D., Rohima, S., Bashir, A., & Mardalena, M. (2022). The role of public spending on education, health, and economic growth toward human development index in the local economy. *Sriwijaya International Journal of Dynamic Economics and Business*, 197-210.
- Nwachukwu, N. J., & Oriavwote, V. E. (2025). IMPACT OF GOVERNMENT RECURRENT EXPENDITURE ON HEALTH ON POVERTY REDUCTION IN NIGERIA. *FUOYE Journal of Management, Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 4(1), 388-401.
- Ogundari, K., & Awokuse, T. (2018). Human capital contribution to economic growth in Sub-Saharan Africa: does health status matter more than education? *Economic Analysis and Policy*, 58(C), 131-140.
- Ojo, T. J., & Ojo, S. I. (2022). Health expenditure, education and economic growth in Nigeria. *Open Journal of Social Science and Humanities*, 3(1), 01-17.
- Okunade, S. O., Olayiwola, A. S., Joseph, K. E., & Olawunmi, A. T. (2025). Does health investment matter for productivity growth in sub-Saharan Africa? Empirical insights from income and regional economic grouping perspectives. *Journal of Economic Structures*, 14(5), 1-22
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s40008-025-00348-3>

- Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) (2021): Growth: Building Jobs and Prosperity in Developing Countries.
<https://www.oecd.org/content/dam/oecd/en/toolkits/derec/evaluation-reports/derec/unitedkingdom/40700982.pdf>
- Rodrik, D. (2008). One economics, many recipes: globalization, institutions, and economic growth. In *One Economics, Many Recipes*. Princeton university press. ISBN: 9780691141176
- Rostow, W. W. (1959). *The stages of economic growth and the problems of peaceful co-existence*. Cambridge, Mass.: Center for International Studies, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, 1959.
- Saidi, Y., & Ochi, A. (2023). Estimating relationships among foreign direct investment, governance quality, and economic growth in developing countries using the threshold auto-regressive model. *Regional Science Policy & Practice*, 15(2), 403-425
- Salami, O.I; Phillips, B. B., & Aworinde, O. B. (2025). Education, poverty and economic growth nexus in anglophone west African countries Olakunle I. Salami. *Journal of Economics and Allied Research*, 10(1), 590-604
- Sanni, L.O & Onakoya, A.B (2025). Human capital development, institutional quality, and gross domestic product per capita: evidence from Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Allied Research*, 10(3), 41-61
- Sasmal, J., & Sasmal, R. (2023). Public expenditure, human capital formation and economic growth in modified Lucas framework: A study in the Indian context. *Journal of Quantitative Economics*, 21(4), 745-768.
- Schultz, T. W. (1961). Investment in human capital. *The American economic review*, 51(1), 1-17.
- Sulisnaningrum, E., Widarni, E. L., & Bawono, S. (2022). Causality Relationship Between Human Capital, Technological Development and Economic Growth. *Organization*, 6(2), 1-12.
- Suwandaru, A., Alghamdi, T., & Nurwanto, N. (2021). Empirical analysis on public expenditure for education and economic growth: Evidence from Indonesia. *Economies*, 9(4), 1-13.
- United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO) (2025): Out-of-school numbers are growing in sub-Saharan Africa
[Out-of-school numbers are growing in sub-Saharan Africa | Global Education Monitoring Report](#)
- Uzawa, H. (1965). Optimum technical change in an aggregative model of economic growth. *International economic review*, 6(1), 18-31.
- Vu Tuan Anh, Tran Ngoc Khanh Linh (2021). Foreign Direct Investment and Economic Growth relationships: The moderation role of institutional quality. *Journal of Social Science Research* 17, 41-54
<https://doi.org/10.24297/jssr.v17i.9013>

Wang, Q. S., Hua, Y. F., Tao, R., & Moldovan, N. C. (2021). Can health human capital help the sub-Saharan Africa out of the poverty trap? An ARDL model approach. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 9, 697826.

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2021.697826>

World Bank (2016): While Poverty in Africa Has Declined, Number of Poor Has Increased

<https://www.worldbank.org/en/region/afr/publication/poverty-rising-africa-poverty-report>

World Bank Poverty and Shared Prosperity Report 2020

<https://www.worldbank.org/en/publication/poverty-and-shared-prosperity-2020>

World Bank (2023): Some 12 million Africans entering the labour market each year-World Bank

<https://www.politiceconomistng.com/12-million-africans-entering-labour-market-year-world-bank/>

World Bank (2024): Global Economic Prospects

<https://thedocs.worldbank.org/en/doc/661f109500bf58fa36a4a46eeace6786-0050012024/related/GEP-Jan-2024-Regional-Highlights-SSA.pdf>

World Bank (2025): Poverty, Prosperity, and Planet: Pathways Out of the Polycrisis

<https://www.worldbank.org/en/events/2025/02/13/3pr-pathways-out-of-the-polycrisis>